

Minutes of the FAIR2Adapt Kick-Off Meeting

Project Name: FAIR2Adapt – FAIR to Adapt to Climate Change

Grant number: 101188256

Dates: 14–15 January 2025

Location: Simula Research Laboratory, 8th Floor (hybrid meeting)

Attendees

42 partner participants and 3 external guests

Project partners

Name	Roles	Organisation
Louise Bolands Eklund	Administrative & Financial Coordinator	SRL
Anne Fouilloux	Project coordinator	SRL
Even Moa Myklebust		SRL
Min Ragan-Kelley		SRL
Markus Stocker	WP4 Leader	TIB
Lauren Snyder		TIB
Michael Fribus	Co-Lead of Communication Task 7.1	TIB
Alexandra Garatzogianni	Lead of Communication Task 7.1	TIB
Daniel Garijo	WP3 Leader	UPM
Tina Odaka	Lead WP6 CS-2 (RiOMar)	IFREMER
Jean-Marc Delouis		IFREMER

Raul Palma	WP2 Leader	PSNC
Claudia Maltoni	WP7 Leader	ALPHA
Riccardo Lannotta	WP7 co-leader	ALPHA
Andres Garcia Silva		Expert.ai
José Manuel Gómez-Pérez	Lead Task 3.4 & Task 4.3	Expert.ai
Jana Sillmann	Lead WP6 CS3 (City of Hamburg)	UHAM
Michael Fischer		City of Hamburg / UHAM
Maja Richter		City of Hamburg / UHAM
Malte von Szombathely		FNK/ UHAM
Tiago Capela Lourenço	WP6 Leader	FC.ID
Inês Gomes Marques		FC.ID
Sukaina Bharwani	Lead WP6 CS-5 (weADAPT & Connectivity Hub) and Task 6.1	SEI
Alejandro Feged Rivadeneira	Lead Task 6.1	SEI
Karel Charvat	Lead Task 3.5, Task 4.4	P4A
Otakar Čerba		P4A
Karel Charvát jr.		P4A/Lesprojekt
Manolis Koubarakis Despina-Athanasia Pantazi		NKUA
Torill Hamre	Lead WP6 CS-1 (Radionucleides/NorESM)	NERSC
Yanchun He		NERSC
Helene R. Langehaug		NERSC
Barbara Magagna	WP5 Leader	GFF
Erik Schultes		GFF
Bert Meerman		GFF
Guido Schmidt	Lead Task 7.2	FTC
Franziska Lotter		FTC

Christine Mataushek		FTC
Julia Bartsch	WP6 CS-6 (EU taxonomy)	ADELPHI
Christian Kind	WP6 CS-6 (EU taxonomy)	ADELPHI
Philipp Koellinger		DESCI
Leonie Raijmakers		DESCI
Edvard Hübinette		DESCI

External guests

Gustavo NEUMANN, Project Officer (online)
Cathrine Lund Myhre, NILU, NO
Markus Fiebig, NILU, NO (online)

Day 1: Tuesday 14 January 9:30-17:30

Arrival and Logistics

- Participants gathered on the 8th floor of Simula Research Laboratory.
- The session began promptly at 10:00.

Opening Session

- **Welcome Statement:** Delivered by Lillian Røstad, CEO, Simula Research Laboratory.
- **Words from the Project Officer (Gustavo Naumann):** The Project Officer emphasized the importance of collaboration with the Twin Project CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC and IRISCC [Home - IRISCC](#); The Green Deal data space was also clearly mentioned. Additionally, the need for prompt communication regarding any delays in reporting was stressed. The Project Officer also encouraged the use of free-of-charge European Commission dissemination tools to promote project results effectively.
 - **ACTION: Identify potential contacts within the IRISCC projects; some partners already have connections with IRISCC collaborators. Reach out to IRISCC. Regarding CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC, we have been in contact with Catherine Freissinet (ARTELIA) and Stian Soiland-Reyes (University of Manchester), but we need to establish a concrete plan for close collaboration, including specific topics and steps to proceed.**

FAIR2Adapt Introduction

- **Presenter:** Anne Fouilloux, SRL
- **Topics Covered:**
 - An overview was provided of the overall objectives, the consortium, governance, Work Package organization and leads, the code of conduct, the communities involved, and their respective case studies. Emphasis was placed on the pivotal role of the case studies in driving and demonstrating the effectiveness of our work.

Invited Keynote

- **Title:** *Implementing FAIR Principles in the ACTRIS Data Centre: Advancing FAIRness in the Atmospheric Subdomain*
- **Speaker:** Cathrine Lund Myhre, NILU
- **Key points:** ACTRIS is a pan-European research infrastructure focused on atmospheric data and processes. This talk highlighted ACTRIS's journey in integrating FAIR principles using FAIR Implementation Profiles within its Data Centre. The key message is that once the technical infrastructure is put in place, the end-users do not need to know all the details of the FAIRification process. Cathrine also discussed the role of FAIR practices in advancing atmospheric research and how it can support climate adaptation. ACTRIS contributes to EU projects like ENVRI-FAIR and ENVRI-Hub NEXT, promoting FAIR data practices and interdisciplinary collaboration across environmental research infrastructures.
 - **ACTION:** The potential of collaboration with NILU is clear; we can learn from their journey but also can leverage data from ACTRIS. Define a clear plan on how to collaborate with ACTRIS within the FAIR2Adapt project.

Group Picture of in-person participants

FAIR2Adapt Strategic Alignment

- **Presentations:**
 - **The EOSC and EOSC Partnership:** Ute Gunsenheimer, The EOSC Association, The Ute presented the EOSC Association, explaining that it advocates for Open Science, aligning EU research policies, promoting FAIR data practices, and enabling seamless data access. The EOSC Association drives collaboration through Task Forces, events like the EOSC Winter School, the EOSC Symposium, and the SRIA (Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda) defines the roadmap. Key goals include advancing interoperability and establishing a functional EOSC Federation by 2025.
 - **ACTION: We need to list who is involved in EOSC (which Task Forces, EOSC Focus Working Groups, etc.)**
 - **Mission Adaptation to Climate Change:** Guido Schmidt (FTC) presented the main objective of the mission to adapt to climate change, which aims to support over 150 European regions and communities towards climate resilience by 2030. He demonstrated the portal, focusing on the Regional Adaptation Support Tool, where Step 1 involves gathering data for the adaptation case—an area where FAIR2Adapt can make a significant contribution. Another key feature of the portal is the community of practice, with various thematic working groups. The most relevant for us is 'Climate Services - P2R Deep Dive.' **Our initial idea to create a new group may**

not be feasible due to ongoing changes within the community, and we will need to explore this further in the coming months.

- **ACTION: Identify which partners are involved in which groups and discuss how these involvements can be leveraged for the FAIR2Adapt project.**
- **Adapting to Climate Risks in Hamburg (Michael Fischer and Maja Richter, City of Hamburg):** Integration of FAIR2Adapt use cases into the Urban Data Platform/Urban Model Platform. The Urban Data Platform and Urban Model Platform were presented with their current functionalities but also what they are interested in getting as part of the project. It will be interesting to see how their work integrates with current data spaces. **Alignment with FAIR2Adapt Communities:** The FAIR2Adapt project aligns with several key initiatives, including **FAIR-Impact** for managing researcher metadata, and **I-ADOPT** with RDA working groups (FAIR4RS, FAIR4ML). We want to collaborate with [CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC](#). The **DestinE** project, using DGGs (Healpix grid) for climate data, is relevant to CS-1 and CS-2 (probably for CS-3 too). Collaboration opportunities include **ACTRIS**, data spaces, and partnerships with **FDOs** (presentation from Erik Schultes) to enhance integration and data sharing. We need to follow up with a clear plan and actions.
 - **ACTION: We need to list and map collaboration opportunities and define a clear plan to turn this potential into effective collaboration. Most importantly, we must identify what we can and want to use from other initiatives and projects. Should we consider inviting individuals from these initiatives or projects to join our external advisory board?**

Technical Work-Package Presentations

- **WP6: Case Studies and End-User Applications (Tiago Capela Lourenço, FC.ID):** WP6 focuses on assessing FAIRification protocols across six independent case studies. Each case study will test the application of FAIR principles in different domains, and there are partnerships with other projects to demonstrate the transfer capabilities of these use cases.
 - Overview of six case studies:
 - CS1: Spread of radioactive isotopes in the Arctic (Torill Hamre, NERSC): Focuses on the spread of radioactive isotopes in the Arctic, assessing their potential harm to animals and residents. Data is available but very large (52 TB) and in NetCDF format. The task is to map variables, enrich metadata, and expose the data for use.
 - CS2: River-dominated Ocean Margins (Tina Odaka, IFREMER): Focuses on ocean modeling and simulation in river-dominated margins. The challenge is data sharing, interoperability, and dissemination. Datasets are in netCDF but too big to be easily manipulated so regridded into DGGs grid and saved into

- Zarr. They “aggregate” all data by creating a catalog in parquet format. They also use STAC (Spatio Temporal Asset Catalog).
- CS3: Hamburg City (Malte von Szombathely, University of Hamburg) in collaboration with the city of Hamburg. Addresses extreme rainfall events and flood risk modeling and will focus on more hazards in the future. There’s a need to develop vocabularies to support different communities and create tools for users to calculate risk maps.
 - CS4: FAIR-by-design national adaptation hub (Tiago Capela Lourenço, FC.ID): The goal is to create a search engine, metadata registry, or platform for storage and integrate scattered data. As much as possible we do not want to create another platform that would be difficult to maintain.
 - CS5: The Connectivity Hub and weADAPT (Sukaina Bharwani, SEI): Focuses on connecting over 1,000 case studies and 5,000 articles through a taxonomy. They want to understand how to make the taxonomy FAIR and track its elements in an inventory.
 - CS6: EU taxonomy for sustainable activities (Julia Bartsch, ADELPHI): Targets the reporting of companies' contributions to environmental objectives, addressing new EU guidelines. They aim to develop FAIR data strategies to meet reporting requirements.
- It seems we can group the case studies into two main categories: 1) CS1, CS2, and CS3, and 2) CS4, CS5, and CS6. The first set of case studies is more data-driven, with a well-known path for FAIRification. The latter three case studies, however, are different, and we need to better understand what the FAIRification framework will look like for them. CS4 is the most open at this stage, and we can use it to demonstrate the full extent of the work done by the technical partners. CS3 can act as a bridge between the data-driven case studies and the more 'knowledge-based' case studies (CS4, CS5, and CS6). For CS5, technical partners (Expert.ai, TIB, GFF) need to understand how knowledge 'extraction' is currently performed from various document types (e.g., CORDIS) in weADAPT and explore how the Connectivity Hub could be better integrated into the technical services used or developed within FAIR2Adapt (in particular the AI-related services), to identify opportunities for improvement or more automation (AI, etc.).
 - **ACTION:**
 - We need to organize discussions with WP5 and WP6 to determine the minimum requirements for establishing the Case Study Stakeholder Group.
 - Each case study should create a list of individuals who should attend the FAIR awareness course.
 - Additionally, each case study needs to organize its first workshop
 - **WP2–WP5:** Presentations of core technical work packages and their objectives

- WP2 (Raul Palma, PSNC): An important focus is aligning with WP5 to FAIRify metadata elements and controlled vocabularies while synchronizing with WP3 and WP4 to integrate services into ROHub. Additionally, we need to identify tools, services, and GUI requirements for visualizing and executing resources (from the FDOs), ensuring usability for research communities and stakeholders. PSNC can support the infrastructure needs for service providers and users. It is essential to leverage ROHub capabilities, particularly by understanding how it should be utilized by the CCA communities through the six case studies. WP2 will also provide comprehensive documentation, tutorials, and helpdesk resources in collaboration with the Task Helpdesk.
 - **ACTION: Determine which task forces need to be established to ensure the smooth integration of all services and the relevance of our developments for the CCA communities. Assess whether the RO-Crate profile developed within RELIANCE for Earth Science Communities is also relevant for FAIR2Adapt and could be selected as the initial version.**
- WP3 (Daniel Garijo, UPM): WP3 focuses on developing a framework to FAIRify Digital Objects (DOs) for the FAIR2Adapt project, aiming to integrate these services into ROHub. Key tasks include defining the FAIRification framework (what it means in practice), automating metadata extraction/enrichment, and enhancing the FAIRness of geospatial data for Climate Change Adaptation. FAIR assessment tools (are existing ones relevant for CCA?), AI-supported metadata extraction, and publishing pipelines will also be developed. Potential collaborations with projects like OSTRAILS have been identified, and we will outline these opportunities and their practical implications. A key risk is the gap between task completion and final service integration, which will require 'reserving' some PMs to address potential developments related to integration from M28 to M36.
 - **ACTION: Review the FAIR assessment tools and determine how to define a baseline for the six case studies to monitor progress in the development of the FAIRification framework and its application to real-world scenarios. We need to clarify Task 3.5 (Lead P4A) about the FAIR (Big) Data publishing pipeline.**
- WP4 (Markus Stocker, TIB): WP4 aims to enhance data analysis and knowledge synthesis in CCA through knowledge synthesis, developing a CCA-tailored question-answering LLM, and publishing knowledge in customizable dashboards. The focus is on making scientific knowledge machine-readable to improve integration and presentation, with an emphasis on small-scale showcases within the FAIR2Adapt case studies
 - **ACTION: Identify the role of DESCI, ensuring that the different services complement each other rather than compete. Determine which task force**

is needed to facilitate this. In collaboration with WP3 and WP5, identify the specific needs of each case study.

- WP5 (Barbara Magagna, GFF): WP5 focuses on enhancing community engagement in FAIR2Adapt through training on FAIR principles, identifying user requirements, co-developing CCA services via hackathons, and providing helpdesk support. Key tasks include capacity building, addressing implementation gaps, and fostering collaboration with other WPs to deliver tailored services and improve data practices.
 - **ACTIONS: Create a list of individuals to invite to the FAIR Awareness Course and collaborate with the WP6 communities to define the Helpdesk Guide. Identify contributors for the FIPs and SIPs for each case study. Together with WP6 (and WP3, etc.), collect user requirements.**

Day 2: Wednesday 15 January 9:00-14:30

Breakout Session

- **Activities:**
 - Work-package and task planning.
 - Data management, processing, and case study requirements analysis.
- We spent about one hour discussing it. The largest group was WP6. For technical WPs, most technical partners are involved in several WPs. This will help with coordination.

Administrative Aspects

- Tools, reporting mechanisms, and the Project Management Plan (PMP) were presented by Louise Bolands Eklund (SRL): google drive has been set-up but not shared with partners
 - **ACTION: move all the current documents we shared into this new google drive and share with the partners. Share the slides with all the partners.**

Reporting and Discussions

- **Findings and Restitution per WP:**
 - **Outputs:** The discussion highlighted the need to quickly define task forces to clarify the work ahead. It's important to align tasks at a more granular level than just the WP, as we've gained a good understanding of the work required at the WP level, but more detail is needed, and this is where confusion still exists. There's a risk of the case studies evolving independently from the technical work and vice versa. To

mitigate this risk, we need to better understand the needs and map them to the technical work.

- **ACTION: Create a list of tasks/points that need clarification, and organize task forces and regular meetings to address them. Identify a technical partner/service for each case study that would be the main beneficiary of their service.**

WP7 Introduction and Discussions

- **Topics Covered:**
 - Communication and dissemination strategies (Michael Fribus, TIB): visual identity already defined, logo is already available.
 - **ACTION: Set up a bluesky account (since X/Twitter cannot be opened/was closed). Clarify GDPR aspects (to avoid each partner individually defining how to handle GDPR; this could be covered in WP1 under Data Management) and responsibilities for internal communication (discuss with SRL in WP1). Collect information from partners, case studies for the website.**
 - Sustainability and exploitation plans (Riccardo Lannotta, ALPHA)
 - Cooperation with EOSC (Raul Palma, PSNC) and adaptation missions (Christine Matauschek (FTC))

Closing Session

- **Next Steps:** See actions in this document. Another important action is to agree on who should be invited to the External Advisory Board. Please add your suggestions below.

Appendices

1. [Agenda](#)
2. [Presentation slides](#).
3. Glossary:
 - EOSC: European Open Science Cloud
 - CCA: Climate Change Adaptation
 - DRR: Disaster Risk Reduction
 - FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.
 - RoHub: Research Object Hub
 - RO-Crate: Research Object Crate
 - FDO: FAIR Digital Object

- FIP: FAIR Implementation Profile
- FID:
- DCAT?
- GEO: Group on Earth Observations?
- Nanopublications?
- CF-Conventions: Climate and Forecast conventions